

Professional Etiquettes among Nursing Students

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ABSTRACT

Professional etiquette, a critical link for carrier success. Etiquette is more than good manners; it's a tool for cultivating good relationship. More than most careers, Nursing is characterized by professional relationship among different people in numerous settings. Professional etiquettes are most important aspect in the student's life. The objective of the study was to assess the professional etiquettes among nursing students. 160 students were selected from B.Sc. Post basic and M.Sc. Nursing subject by disproportionate Simple Random Sampling Technique at Saraswati Nursing Institute, Dhianpura, Punjab. From each class of (B.Sc. and Post basic) 25 student and from M.Sc. 10 students were taken in the study. (Professional Etiquettes Self Structured Likert)(PESL) scale was prepared to assess the professional etiquettes. Content validity of the tool was determined. Reliability ($r=0.75$) of the tool was tested by split half method and Karl Pearson coefficient correlation formula. A pilot study was conducted by interviewing 15 respondents who fulfil the sampling criteria with the help of help of (PESL) scale. The data collected from the respondents was analysed by using descriptive statistics. The tool was found feasible and practicable. Assessment of professional etiquettes of the nursing students revealed that majority of students 93.75% of students rated themselves as highly followed professional etiquettes whereas 6.25% students rated themselves as average followed professional etiquettes. The overall 87.82% of students rated themselves as highly followed professional etiquettes. Domain wise assessment scored showed highest percentage 91.65% of students rated themselves in etiquettes in library whereas low 82.14% of students rated themselves in etiquettes in classroom. there is significant difference with demographical variable. So finding of the study revealed that 87.82% students were rated themselves high professional etiquettes. The study conclude that majority of nursing students rated themselves highly professional etiquettes.

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KEYWORDS: Professional Etiquettes, Fundamental of Nursing, Professionalism

I. INTRODUCTION:

Professional etiquette, a critical link for carrier success. Etiquette is more than good manners; it's a tool for cultivating good relationship. More than most careers, Nursing is characterized by professional relationship among different people in numerous settings. Based on the guiding principles of kindness, consideration, and common sense, professional etiquette can help us from new alliances and enhance established ones. Use these professional etiquette tips to polish communication skill and strengthen the relationship with colleagues.¹

we noticed that in nursing professional etiquettes and discipline is very important. Nurses have to deal with their seniors, juniors, Doctors and patients. so, they should have to learn etiquettes from the beginning of their study. so, we want to assess the professional etiquettes in undergraduate and postgraduate students my college. we want to assess that how they deal with their teachers, seniors and juniors in college and clinical area. we want to check that how they behave in clinical area with staff nurses and doctors, in mess with mess workers and in hostel with warden maam².

1.1. Need of study:-

Need for study arises because statistics proved that most prevalent or essential cause of all nursing college dropout

because of obedience of poor professional etiquettes which affect learning and academic achievement leading to failure. Professional etiquette is a major concept of education and if it will not improve more and more student will be rejected from various opportunities. Etiquette were affected by various factor such as motivation and interest to subject, educational facilities.³

1.2. Statement of problem:-

A descriptive study to assess the professional etiquettes among nursing students in Saraswati Nursing Institute, Dhianpura, Punjab.

1.3. Objective:-

To assess the professional etiquettes among nursing students of Saraswati Nursing Institute, Dhianpura, Punjab.

1.4. Assumption:-

Student will have follow some professional etiquettes

1.5. Delimitation:-

1. Nursing students of Saraswati Nursing Institute, Dhianpura, Punjab
2. Assess professional etiquette only.
3. Only one time data collection.

II. METHODOLOGY

A descriptive study has been conducted to assess professional etiquettes among nursing students. Random sampling was used to selected the study subjects.160 study sample were selected to conducted the study. Self-reported structured Likert scale (consisted 45 statements) was selected for nursing students to collect data to assess the professional etiquettes among nursing students. Tools were prepared in English. Experts from the field of nursing determined the content validity of the tools. Reliability of scale was computed where both the tools were found to be reliable with P= 0.7. Self-reported structure Likert scale responses allow subjects to give their agreement on a

continuum (Always= 4, Most of the time=3, Sometime = 2, Never = 1). Ethical clearance was obtained from institutional ethical committee of Saraswati Nursing Institute Kurali. Written informed consent was taken from the subject of study. Anonymity of subjects were assured by assigning code for them. All the subjects were informed that their participation is completely voluntary. study was conducted in the month of March to July 2019. Data was analysed by using SPSSV.22. Data was collected from the Saraswati nursing institute. The purpose of the study was explained to the subjects and confidentiality was assured to all the subjects.

III. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Table No3.1: Frequency and percentage distribution of demographic characteristics of nursing N= 160

S. No.	Demographic variable	Frequency	%
1.	Age in years		
1.1	18-21	91	56.8%
1.2	22-25	62	38.8%
1.3	26-29	7	4.4%
2.	Academic Course		
2.1	B.Sc nursing	101	63.2%
2.2	Post basic nursing	49	30.6%
2.3	M.Sc nursing	10	6.2%
3.	Year of study		
3.1	1 st year	60	37.5%
3.2	2 nd year	50	31.3%
3.3	3 rd year	25	15.6%
3.4	4 th year	25	15.6%

Table No3.2: Overall mean score of professional etiquettes of nursing students N=160

S. No	Maximum possible score	Minimum possible score	Range	x+SD	Mean%
1.	179	106	73	157.2±13.35	87.82%

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO 3.1

Table No.3.1: Data revealed that the frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic characteristics of nursing students or subject which shows: Majority of the students fall in the age group 18-21 (56.9%) whereas (38.8%) of the students fall in the age group 22-25, and (4.4%) of the students fall in age group 26-29 years.

➤ One of the important aims of nursing research is to contribute knowledge to the body of nursing and to expand and broaden the scope of nursing. And, this study's most significant contribution is the development of the self structured Likert scale and it open ways for exploration in area related to assessment of nursing competency.

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO.3.2

Table No 3.2: Data shows that the maximum possible score of professional etiquettes self structured likert scale was 179, and minimal score of professional etiquettes self structured likert scale was 106, the range of score is 73 and the calculated mean of the 160 sample is 157.2 and SD of those 160 sample was 13.35 ($x \pm SD = 157.2 \pm 13.35$), and the total mean percentage of the students regarding professional etiquettes is 87.82%.

Therefor result inferred that maximum number of students had follow good professional etiquettes.

IV. NURSING IMPLICATION

- The self structured Likert scale provides nurse educators with an ability to assess the professional etiquettes among nursing students.
- Nurse Administrator can use this scale to evaluate the competencies of their professional etiquettes.
- Nurse educator have the opportunity to enhance student's professional etiquettes.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the finding of the present study it is concluded that the most of the nursing students had follow the library etiquettes. The following conclusion were drawn on the basis of present study. From the findings of the study it can be concluded that the demographic variables such as age, academic course, year of study no significant association with follow the professional etiquettes.

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